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Summary

The activities of WP2 - C Farming data collection aim to provide a comprehensive review of vineyard management practices to maximise soil organic carbon (SOC) storage capacity for sustainable vineyard management. Initially, a literature review was carried out with the aim of creating an inventory of best practices for "carbon stocking" by collecting information from previous and ongoing projects, technical reports and scientific articles and organising it into a database (D.1.1).

This document provides a handbook of best practices for carbon stocking in viticulture. The handbook is divided into three sections based on the similarity of carbon storage practices; within each section there are a number of fact sheets outlining each storage practice, agri-environmental and economic advantages and disadvantages.

Introduction

Current ecological and environmental emergencies, such as the rapid consumption and degradation of agricultural land, climate change, the depletion of natural resources with the loss of natural and cultivated biodiversity, and the loss of productivity of agricultural land, require sustainable development strategies, particularly in agriculture.

After years of land and crop management practices aimed solely at maximising profits and unsustainable from the point of view of non-renewable resources, particularly soil, there is now a widespread awareness that agriculture must take into account the complex natural balances that underpin the relationship between soil, plant and atmosphere in order to prevent environmental degradation and produce healthier products. Among the most vulnerable productive agricultural sectors is viticulture, a strategic sector in the production chains of many European rural economies, for which the need to adopt strategies for greater environmental, economic and social sustainability has become apparent.

Sustainability in viticulture involves identifying production models in which quality wine production can go together with the adoption of agronomic techniques protecting the environment and its resources. To this end, certain soil characteristics, such as the quantity and quality of organic matter (OM), structure and degree of compaction, as well as those related to the quantity and activity of microbial biomass, appear to play an effective role as indicators of environmental quality.

Agricultural ecosystems in general, and tree ecosystems in particular, are considered to have a significant role in influencing environmental quality globally. In particular, they are considered strategic for climate change mitigation because they remove CO₂ from the atmosphere and then store it in organic form in plant and soil components (Giovannini et al. 2003; Robertson et al., 2000). It is therefore scientifically relevant and economically strategic to obtain information on the sequestration capacity (carbon sink) of the most widespread tree crops.

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) defines carbon sequestration as any process, activity or mechanism that removes greenhouse gases, aerosols or a greenhouse gas precursor from the atmosphere. A carbon sink is defined as a natural or man-made "reservoir" that absorbs and stores carbon from the atmosphere through physical and biological mechanisms; carbon stocking activities contribute to the carbon sink. Carbon farming, literally 'carbon farming', involves the definition and implementation of payment schemes for soil carbon sequestration practices.

In the viticulture ecosystem, various agricultural, plant and soil management activities/practices promote the efficiency of capturing and storing atmospheric CO₂ in the two reservoirs, plant and soil (carbon sinks). Such practices also help to improve soil quality and the long-term sustainability of the wine sector, as well as provide long-term economic benefits (Giffard et al., 2022).

Ecosystem services are the set of services provided by natural systems for the benefit of humans; in this context, in addition to agricultural production and thus income, vineyards provide humans with five main ecosystem services (erosion control, water regulation, carbon sequestration,

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biodiversity protection and landscape quality). This handbook focuses on the carbon sink function of the vineyard, which can be maximised through careful and planned management practices. It describes the main carbon sequestration measures in viticulture, each agronomic technique is illustrated with its advantages and disadvantages from both an agri-environmental and economic perspective.

Good carbon sequestration practices were grouped into the following three homogeneous groups based on the similarity of carbon sequestration practices:

1. Soil management
2. Soil conditioners and fertilizers
3. Irrigation

The techniques indicated in the different sectors are general and must be applied taking into account the environmental and agronomic characteristics of the plots, which are often different, even on the same farm, in terms of location, exposure, microclimate, soil and vine variety. In addition, the feasibility and cost-effectiveness dictated by the specific conditions of the farm must always be taken into account.

1- Cultivation: soil management

General Background

Among the agronomic techniques, tillage is the one to which the greatest attention has been paid since ancient times and to which considerable efforts have been made to improve its efficiency.

The use of soil management techniques to promote carbon sequestration in vineyards, in addition to increasing the organic matter content of the soil, makes it possible to reduce degradation phenomena such as erosion or compaction, to combat drought, to improve the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil, to control weeds and to combat pathogens.

It is always necessary to make a critical assessment of the management measures that can be adopted in order to avoid negative effects such as: erosion, deterioration of physical, chemical and biological fertility, excesses or deficiencies in plant vigour with poor quality production.

Here we will not go into the issues of soil preparation for planting and planting rooted cuttings, but will concentrate on annual soil management.

In general, the common purpose of tillage is to create, restore or maintain the best habitable conditions for cultivated plants by modifying one or more of the soil's physical, chemical and biological properties, particularly its structure (Mazzilli, 2021). Modifying the structure and thus the softness of the soil is the main purpose of tillage, but it is not the only one. Tillage has a series of objectives, sometimes even independent of the previous one.

In the vineyard, tillage is carried out both between the rows and in the rows, and the objectives common to both can be summarised as follows:

- establishing a structural condition suitable for root penetration and their proper functioning;
- removing the surface roots of the vines and promoting the development of a deeper root system;
- increasing the permeability of the active layer and thus controlling water circulation, reducing stagnation, surface run-off and erosion;
- increasing the thickness of the soil that can be explored by the roots and thus, in some cases, the amount of water that can be stored as a useful water reserve during the wettest months, allowing cultivated plants to better cope with periods of insufficient natural or artificial water supply;
- destruction or containment of wild vegetation and some plant or animal pests;
- disruption of surface capillarity;
- burial of fertiliser and crop residues;
- seedbed preparation for green manure crops to create a favourable environment for seed germination.

However, there are equally valid reasons for rethinking traditional processing techniques. The following are some of the most common negative effects:

- formation of a layer of increased hardness at the bottom of the ploughed soil, which can prevent the penetration of water and roots under the ploughed layer;
- greater mineralisation of organic matter, which makes nutrients more readily available to plants, but also jeopardises the maintenance of the structural state of soils deficient in organic matter;
- stirring up of soil layers, sometimes useful but often harmful;
- increased water and wind erosion of the soil surface;
- too deep burial of crop residues;
- high energy costs, from non-renewable sources.

Physical parameters	
Positive effects on yield	Negative effects on yield
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• permeability• water retention capacity• temperature• aeration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• degradation of soil organic matter• water erosion on sloping soils• wind erosion• soil compaction• creation of impermeable layers

Tab. 1: Some changes in physical parameters after traditional ploughing and tilling

The techniques proposed to overcome the above problems are:

- no tillage, zero tillage or direct seeding
- minimum tillage

In addition to techniques that reduce the intensity of tillage, there are other soil management systems that are considered conservative, i.e. they reduce the impact on the environment and organic matter, such as

- - Grass cover
- - Green manuring with nitrogen fixing crops
- - Green manuring with a mix of crops
- - Natural mulching
- - Mulching with aromatic or other cash crops

1.1 – NO TILLAGE

Technique description

No tillage is used to cultivate crops without disturbing the soil through tillage methods. This technique has the advantage of preventing the breakdown of the soil structure by avoiding the passage of machines that cause its compaction. There is a stabilisation over time, with the formation of a permanent, more continuous and interconnected porosity, which replaces the temporary

porosity obtained mechanically and creates a better functional balance in the soil between infiltration, drainage and aeration. This promotes entomological and microbiological biodiversity in the soil, making it healthier and more stable.

No-tillage reduces surface run-off and soil erosion, especially on sandy, dry soils and slopes. Another important advantage of the technique is better adaptation to drought, as no-tillage allows better water absorption and infiltration due to improved porosity, which also increases irrigation efficiency. This effect is also useful in case of heavy rainfall and wind, preventing excessive surface runoff and water/wind erosion.

In no-till soils, the rapid oxidation of organic matter to CO₂ is limited, and the accumulation over time of crop residues and root exudates of carbon metabolites results in a transition from C-loss to C-accumulation, promoting a virtuous process of atmospheric carbon sequestration in the long term.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: **positive.**

It preserves soil structure, reduces the risk of soil erosion and run-off, improves water absorption and infiltration, and increases irrigation efficiency. It also has a positive impact on biodiversity.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: **suitable for hill and mountain soils.**

Better results are obtained in temperate climates, with a regular distribution of rainfall throughout the year, with erosive phenomena evident, and with soils not too rich in clay.

Technical limitations: **need for monitoring the physical state of the soil.**

the temporary beneficial effect of tillage is lost: poor soil levelling, uneven distribution of crop residues, excessive trampling of harvest areas can lead to adverse physical conditions and consequently to increased pest and fungal infestation.

Investment **Low**

cost In vineyards, no-tillage does not involve any particular type of intervention.

Average cost **Between 100 and 200 euro/ha**

per year per hectare There is no need for tillage, apart from a single direct sowing operation for grass between the rows unless natural cover is not chosen.

Cost compared **Low**

with conventional practice A single pass through the field is planned, resulting in lower costs per hectare and reduced tillage time.

Public support **PSP – Rural Development Interventions**

SRD01 – agricultural productive investments for farm competitiveness.

SRD02 – agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare.

1.2 – MINIMUM TILLAGE

Technique description

Minimum tillage is a technique where soil is managed without inverting the layers (as it is done by ploughing) and with less disturbance of soil, limited to the superficial layers (10 to 20 cm). Along with no-tillage, minimum tillage has the advantage of minimising disturbance to the natural composition, structure and biodiversity of the soil, promoting water infiltration and moisture retention, counteracting erosion and helping to improve water

quality.

Crop residues are left on the surface: this reduces the decomposition of organic matter, increases the storage of organic carbon in the soil and ultimately reduces greenhouse gas emissions.

In viticulture, a minimal surface tillage of the sub-row can be used to break up the surface crust. In addition, a one-time minimum tillage can be used to seed the inter-row turf. Operations carried out with disc harrows or other carried, semi-carried or towed implements with working parts that are not moved by hydraulic or power take-off are part of minimum tillage.

Another minimum tillage technique is the use of the ripper to cut soil without layers inversion in autumn after the grape harvest. The regeneration of vineyard soils, which are compacted each year by the passage of an average number of machines, cannot rely solely on tillage, which can lead to the degradation of organic matter. Such practices must therefore be minimised by adopting the least disturbing ones. Using a ripper or other more or less superficial discing tools, a cut can be made without turning the layers to break up the compact soil, aerate it and thus promote the oxidation of organic matter and the development of micro-organisms.

From a technical point of view, minimum tillage reduces fixed costs such as fuel and lubricant costs, labour hours and wear and tear on agricultural machinery.

Minimum tillage is also useful in combating soil erosion caused by heavy rain and wind.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: positive.

This method preserves soil structure, reduces the risk of soil erosion and runoff, improves water absorption and infiltration, and increases irrigation efficiency. It also has a positive impact on biodiversity.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: need for weed control.

The absence of mechanical control of the weeds implies if one does not want to lose yield, a minimum dependence on the use of chemical herbicides.

Technical limitations:

No-till in the inter-row space includes all weed control methods other than mechanical weeding, which must be used carefully so as not to create problems for the plants.

Cost

Investment cost	<p>Variable</p> <p>The type of equipment used is often already present on the farm. In some cases, an investment may be required to replace PTO driven equipment with trailed equipment. In this case, the cost of the investment, which can be estimated at between €3,000 and €20,000 depending on the size of the farm and the power of the equipment used, could be partially offset by the sale of the previous equipment.</p>
Average cost per year per hectare	<p>150-250 euro/ha</p> <p>Few tillage operations are required. Operating costs are in the range of 150-250 euro/ha (fuel costs, labour costs, etc., alternative costs for contractors).</p>
Cost compared with conventional practice	<p>Low-medium</p> <p>Fewer steps are implemented and with equipment that generally requires less energy consumption and less time.</p>
Public support	<p>PSP – Rural Development Interventions</p> <p>SRD01 – agricultural productive investment for farm competitiveness. SRD02 – agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare.</p>

GRASS COVER

Technique description

Grassing is a management technique that is being adopted more and more frequently and represents a growing trend among the various soil management practices. Data confirm that the area of vineyards covered with grass has increased in Italy in recent years. However, there is a big difference between Northern Italy and Southern Italy, where it is still difficult to establish this technique.

This is due to the fact that in the arid environments of the south, the low summer rainfall and the high

evapotranspiration requirements of the crops could lead to excessive competition for water between the main crop and any vegetative cover.

Permanent spontaneous grass cover, which allows the spontaneous growth of herbaceous essences in different environments, is site-specific and closely related to the climate and soil of a given area. It plays an important role in vineyard management, not only for erosion control, but also as a means of soil management, due to the positive effects of the herbaceous cover on the complex relationship between soil, roots and air of the crop.

Grassing, the intercropping of herbaceous species with tree crops, is proposed as a soil management technique with low environmental and economic impact: in fact, it acts as a "balance" of all the physical, chemical and biological phenomena in the soil-plant system.

Normally, when soil is covered with grass, mowed at 10-15 cm, tillage is not used anymore. As a result, the vineyard is very well protected from erosion and its structure and workability are greatly improved. The roots of herbaceous plants also play an important role in translocating surface nutrients to deeper layers, as will be discussed later.

In grass-covered soils, the increase in organic matter supply allows an increase in water retention capacity and available water in the first 20-30 cm. The increase in top soil water holding capacity provides considerable protection against compaction and the consequent degradation of soil structure caused by the frequent passage of machinery between the rows.

In grassed vineyards, in the presence of leguminous plants, the increase in the organic matter might be accompanied by an increase in assimilable phosphorus and exchangeable potassium in the first 60 cm of soil depth. Enrichment of the deeper soil layers with low mobile elements such as P and K promotes better regulation of vine growth processes and vigour, with beneficial effects on the quality and quantity of grapes produced.

The simplest and most common way to achieve good turf development on the vineyard's inter-row surface is to allow spontaneous flora to grow and, once it achieves a good development and cover, periodically mowing. However, spontaneous vegetation can produce a coarse ground cover in a short period. Indeed, by producing seeds at the end of their cycle, some pioneer essences will propagate their own species and prevent others from establishing. The result can be a non-

homogeneous vegetation cover composed of species that often are not optimal for erosion control or organic matter increase in the soil.

For these reasons, as an alternative to spontaneous grass cover, the use of pure species or appropriate mixtures is justified in practice.

In the case of pure species or mixtures, it is always important to choose a type of grass that is suitable for the environment and the soil. The most common are seasonal, autumn-winter species, often managed as green manure. Cereal cover crops, especially oats and triticale, are very interesting and give excellent results. These crops are mown or chopped at the booting stage, leaving a good cover which, together with the fascicled root system, efficiently prevents erosion. Other interesting species are faba beans or protein peas, for their capacity to fix nitrogen, but since they do not provide sufficient protection against the risks of erosion, they can be seeded in a mix with cereals.

The use of self-seeded species, such as subterranean clover or *Medicago polymorpha* or *Medicago truncatula*, is noteworthy in the case of long-term grasslands. These species grow in cool seasons and spontaneously regenerate from seeds after the summer.

In any case, grass should be considered as a second crop, which involves the removal of water and the temporary immobilisation of nutrients. In fact, turf, whether spontaneous or artificial, usually causes a reduction in grape production in the first few years compared to traditional tillage, sometimes combined with an increase in sugar content. The increase in sugar content seems to depend largely on the reduction in production, while the lack of ripening, which is sometimes observed on grassed soils, seems to be due to the lack of water available to the vine as a result of competition with herbaceous species.

In general, to ensure good coexistence between the vineyard and the permanent pasture, two types of mechanical intervention are essential: (i) decompaction of the rows immediately after harvest by deep subsoiling with localised passage of special aerators, and (ii) light subsoiling near the row by means of rippers, at the beginning of the season and in early summer to counteract temperature and water stress.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: positive.

This method promotes an increase organic matter in the soil, improves structure, reduces the use of chemical fertilisers and increases the water-holding capacity of the soil, reducing the need for crop irrigation. Soil stabilisation and consolidation promotes a reduction in surface erosion.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: need to control herbaceous associations.

The wild community of native species often has the following limitations

- slow and uneven ground cover;
- poor soil protection against erosion and compaction;
- not all adventitious species are equally useful due to high water consumption, excessive height development or risk of infestation;
- late species do not make sufficient use of moisture in the autumn-winter months.

In addition, during periods of low summer rainfall and high evapotranspiration, the turf will extract water and immobilise nutrients, competing with the main crop.

Technical limitations: inadequate machinery and lack of training.

The lack of inter-row seeders is reported in most vineyards. Another aspect is the lack of information and training for farmers and agro-technicians on varietal characteristics, possible combinations and mixtures to be used for grassland management according to soil and climatic aspects.

Costs

Investment cost	Not excessive The measure does not require any investment in special equipment other than that for mowing the lawn. In the case of artificial turf, the cost of the seed must be taken into account, which can range from 600 to 1,000 euros; the lawn can last around 10 years if it is properly maintained.
Average cost per year per hectare	Between 100 and 300 euros/ha. For natural turf, only the cost of mowing and planting should be considered. In the case of artificial turf, an annual seed cost of around €60-100 must be added.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Low By eliminating tillage, less energy and time are needed, reducing costs compared to conventional methods.
Public support	PSP – Rural Development Interventions and Direct Payments. SRA05 – ACA5 – rassing of tree crops. Ecoscheme 2 for partial grassing, inter-row only.

GREEN MANURE WITH NITROGEN-FIXING CROPS

Technical Description

The focus on cover crops in viticulture has shifted from the widespread use of spontaneous grass cover to the more recent practice of sowing species whose value in maintaining organic matter is now well established, in addition to other benefits such as improving soil structure and increasing both ecological and functional biodiversity. Green manure is an agronomic practice that consists of planting a herbaceous crop that is later incorporated to the soil. It generally acts as a fertiliser for the vineyard in which it is sown. A green manure consisting of legumes, either alone or in a mixture, such as field beans, faba bean minor, red clover or velvet vetch, significantly increases the nitrogen content of the soil through nitrogen-fixing activity. If the chosen essences have very deep root systems, they enrich the surface layers of the soil with nutrients taken from the deeper layers.

All green manures are capable of stimulating the proliferation of soil microflora, which in turn has a preventive and inhibitory effect on the proliferation of pathogenic micro-organisms. It has a positive effect on biodiversity and some essences are important in attracting beneficial insects such as bees.

The most favorable time for burying leguminous cover crops is usually the time of early flowering, which for many species corresponds to the time when biomass is close to peak and biomass decomposition is still good. At this stage, the strong competition for water between the cover crop and the vineyard has not yet been established, the buried biomass is rich in water and easily attacked by soil micro-organisms such as bacteria and fungi, which are responsible for the development of organic matter in the soil, depending on the presence of certain factors and the quality of the biomass (C/N ratio).

The advantages of this practice lie in maintaining soil fertility and reducing the use of mineral fertilisers. In the case of green manuring, the development of the root system and the burying of the plant biomass introduce a large amount of organic matter into the soil, improving its structure and chemical and biological properties in the short term.

This technique of soil management is very virtuous, especially from a sustainable agriculture perspective, as it not only restores but also improves soil fertility and biodiversity.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: positive.

This method preserves soil structure, reduces the risk of soil erosion and runoff, improves water absorption and infiltration, and increases irrigation efficiency. It also positively affects biodiversity. Nitrogen fixation operated by legumes contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: less anti-erosive action.

Green manure does not have any real limitations, but there are disadvantages in comparison to permanent cover. For example, green manure has a lower a soil erosion function comparable to that of grass, because establishment is slower in autumn and coverage is uneven, at least in the initial stages.

Technical limitations: need for mechanical tillage.

Mechanical tillage is required, making the technique not operable in all soil types.

Costs

Investment cost	Not excessive The measure does not require any investment in special equipment other than the mower.
Average cost per year per hectare	Between 200 to 450 euros/ha The cost per hectare of mowing, sowing and planting, including the cost of seed, can range from 200 to 450 euros per hectare.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Slightly higher The green manure technique requires higher costs associated with tillage and planting. However, these higher costs are often offset by the agronomic benefits.

GREEN MANURE WITH MIX OF DIFFERENT CROPS

Technique Description

Green manure is an agronomic practice that consists of sowing a community of herbaceous essences in purity or consociation, intended to be totally buried or mulched with a fertilizing function within the vineyard. It is done by preparing a seedbed between the rows, preferably in the fall, and sowing in it a mix of herbaceous essences to be mulched and incorporated into the soil in

the spring, once a sufficient level of development has been reached, or to be rolled or mowed. The essences, mostly forage crops, are chopped close to flowering, allowed to dehydrate for a few days and incorporated into the top 25 cm of soil. Once buried, the biomass is attacked by macros and microorganisms that transform it partly into humus and partly into readily usable nutrients (in particular, nitrogen).

Green manure with grasses, particularly oats, barley, spelt or triticale, will shift decomposition toward humus formation, as they are very rich in fiber. When mowed very young, or when grown in mixtures with legumes, a more balanced mineralization/humification is achieved, with grasses providing carbon (fiber) and legumes providing nitrogen (protein). In any case, the dynamics of decomposition and post-intercropping nutrient release vary depending on the chemical composition of residues, climate, soil texture and structure.

With green manure, a whole range of micro- and meso-elements (calcium, iron, boron, etc.) are mobilized that might otherwise be unavailable in the soil, even if present. The quali-quantitative combination of herbaceous species in the mixture must be carefully considered to avoid negative interspecific interactions, in order to guide the quality of biomass produced according to the needs of the cash crop in which the green manure is implemented, and the specific soil and climate situation.

It is worth mentioning, however, that grapevines, in general, are not a good competitor against cultivated or weedy herbaceous species because of the low density of their root system compared to that of herbaceous species.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: positive.

This method preserves soil structure, reduces the risk of soil erosion and runoff, improves water absorption and infiltration, and increases irrigation efficiency. It positively affects biodiversity. In addition, this type of green manure also performs an important aesthetic action, through blooms of various colors (red flower incarnate clover, yellow flower brassicas, blue flower phacelia, etc.).

Biophysical and environmental limitations: water and nutrients competition.

Despite their many advantages, green manure crops exert water and nutritional competition against vines that can sometimes be significant. The level of such competition depends on many factors, including weather patterns, the water requirements of the vineyard, and the level of root system competition.

Technical limitations: need for tillage.

The mechanical tillage required for green manure, makes the technique not operable in all soil types: the effect of soil compaction with change in structure and reduction of aeration and water infiltration must be considered.

Costs

Investment cost	Low The measure does not require investment in special equipment other than mowing equipment.
Average cost per year per hectare	Contained between 200 to 450 euros/ha Only mowing, seeding and planting are included. The cost per hectare, including the cost of seed can be between 200 and 450 euros per hectare.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Slightly higher There are higher costs associated with tillage and planting. However, these higher costs can be offset by the agronomic benefits.

SHEET 1.6 – NATURAL MULCHING

Technical Description

Vineyard mulching consists of managing the turf (spontaneous or sown) by mowing to create a dry plant mulch. Various organic materials, such as shredded plant waste, or straw, can also be used to create a uniform cover over the soil surface that can act as a solar panel in winter and insulation in summer. Stubble is left in place without being buried. The dried culms create a mulch that, without competing for water

facilitates permeability and protects the soil from rain, sun and compaction. This natural cover reliably protects the soil from drying out, runoff and erosion.

Natural mulching allows inter-row and sub-row to be managed simultaneously. It can be carried out through the use of mulchers and windrow mowers, which can accumulate in the sub-row the plant material removed from the inter-row, forming a thick layer capable of smothering the wild plants present and preventing the germination of their seeds, implementing a weed containment mechanism characterized by a good degree of environmental sustainability.

Organic materials that can be used include:

- fragmented wood: derived from the shredding of young woody twigs, resulting from the shredding of hedges, vine shoots, etc. internally on the farm, or from external supply (from gardening operations on municipal property, forests, scrubland, clearings);
- husks and straw (of buckwheat, rice, sunflower, millet, barley, wheat, rye, etc.).
- herbaceous waste from weeding, taking care not to mulch the soil with biomass from weed species weeded after flowering to avoid spreading seeds.

Straw and bark from crop residues or other sources. Straw is preferable long, not shredded, making a layer up to 20 cm thick, which perfectly prevents soil from drying out, prevents the development of fungal diseases and the spread of slugs. The optimal size of bark pieces is 2x2 cm (medium-sized wood). Organic mulch degrades over time, enriching the soil with useful substances, improving its structure and changing its pH. The benefits of mulching remain strongly linked to the type of biomass used (more or less rich in carbon, nitrogen or minerals). The amounts to be contributed are

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important in order to obtain a cover of at least 5 cm, from which one can expect to limit weed development. Mowing can take place when the weeds reach a height of about 40 cm, consequently 4-5 passes of chopping are generally carried out during a growing season.

Mulching can be done in spring or fall: early or late spring (depending on weather conditions) are the best times to mulch. After the winter rains and melting snow, the soil is moist and the warm spring sun warms it perfectly. If the previous year's mulch layer has not decomposed and been destroyed, it should be removed to allow the soil to warm up. Before mulching, it should be weeded and fertilized if necessary. Spring mulching protects plants from overheating and summer drying. Another ideal time for mulching is in mid-autumn, when the soil is still warm and with sufficient moisture given by autumn rains. Before spreading the mulch, weeds should be removed and fertilizer (such as ash or decomposed manure) is applied if necessary. Fall mulch protects the soil and plants from exposure and freezing of the root system. Mulch should be spread over the row, avoiding contact with grape tendrils. The mulch layer should be renewed every year or every few years, depending on the material chosen.

The positive effects of mulching can be summarized as follows: protection of the soil from the impact of rain and consequent reduction of water erosion, improved infiltration capacity and increased water storage in the soil, decreased evaporation, improved soil structure and organic matter content in the soil, improved root development of cash crops, and increased micro- and macrofauna such as certain species of earthworms useful to the soil.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: **positive.**

This method preserves soil structure, reduces the risk of soil erosion and runoff, improves water uptake and infiltration, and increases irrigation efficiency.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **phytosanitary monitoring required.**

Mulch material, if unsuitable, can generate weeds or provide a refuge for various pest organisms. In addition, maintaining moisture under the row can promote the development of fungal diseases.

Technical limitations: **specific mechanical work.**

Maintaining an adequate level of cover (at least 2 inches thick of mulch) increases the of operating costs. In addition, using wood chips or straw also requires consideration of the cost of the material. Grass cutting should be done with light and less compacting means, coupling under-row tillage in the same pass. It is essential not to use the classic hammer mowers, which should be replaced with cutter bar or rotary knife mowers or chain mowers in stony soils.

Costs

Investment cost	Medium
Average cost per year per hectare	The cost is related to mowing, which is a practice already expected when grassing, and to the arrangement of the material. Only in relation to this specific technique can an average cost be estimated; grassing varies between 150 and 300 euros per hectare. Under-row placement of some of the mowing can be estimated at between 50 and 100 euros per hectare. Mulching can often be done by chopping woody residues in conjunction with mowing the grassland giving rise to mulching to be arranged under the row with an average cost of 120-150 euros/ha. For viticulture, in the case of natural under-row mulching, a cost per hectare per year is therefore estimated to range from 200 to 450 euros.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Higher Ranging between 200 to 450 euros/ha

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Public support	PSP - Rural Development Interventions: SRA21 - Action 2 Management of pruning residues on the ground;
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SHEET 1.7 – INTERCROPPING WITH AROMATICS

Technical Description

Intercropping refers to the cultivation of two or more species in the same production area at the same time. If this relationship is well set up it brings benefits to both crops or at least to one of them without compromising the proper development of the other.

It is a mixed cropping technique that takes advantage of the different eco-physiological characteristics of the crop species by optimizing their interactions, for example by harmonizing the cultivation of herbs with that of vegetable crops. The associations are not accidental and are the result, even before scientific studies, of careful observations of growers, gardeners or simple enthusiasts made throughout history.

Plant intercropping in the vineyard is an integral part of the Italian tradition, although in many areas this approach has been lost. In the thousand-year history of Italy's vineyards, the most common viticulture was promiscuous, with rows of vines alternating with other crops. Scientific research confirms how the intercropping of vines with other plant species can help improve various aspects of viticulture, as part of overall agronomic management aimed at sustainability.

Some examples of intercropping with aromatics include sage, thyme, and lavender. Aromatics give off certain substances that are capable of attracting beneficial insects while at the same time warding off harmful ones. For this reason, plants grown alongside aromatics are generally less susceptible to disease, pest attack, or competition with pests. Most aromatics, if allowed to flourish, attract butterflies, bees and other beneficial insects that find there an important nectar resource, as well as promoting pollination of all surrounding vegetation. In addition to the number of beneficial insects, another positive aspect of intercropping with aromatic species is the scenic and recreational value given by the multiplicity of colours that can be observed in bloom.

Thus, intercropping with aromatics represents an approach that combines sustainability, beauty and functionality. Through careful plant selection, intelligent soil and water management, and the use of synergistic techniques, it is possible to create a vineyard that is not only a healthy and self-sustaining ecosystem, but also an aesthetic attraction.

Environmental benefits beyond the accumulation of Carbon in the soil: positive

An environment rich in diverse plant species allows for greater preservation of biodiversity; the vineyard becomes a “green corridor” for small animals in their movements among woods, scrub and shrubs. The presence of shrubs and grasses affects the micro-climate of the vineyard. Positive effects also concern the reduction of soil erosion.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: the species to be intercropped must be well thought out

Among the limitations arising from intercropping with aromatics is competition for nutrients and water: intercropping with species with high nutritional requirements could lead to soil depletion to the detriment of the cash crop. For the same reason, species with high water consumption create unfavorable competition with the main crop.

Technical limitations: specific mechanical tillage

Managing under-row intercropping on a large scale requires mechanization of seeding and management operations, which are specific since they are carried out between the stumps: to work properly, mowers must advance at a very low speed, and there is still always the risk of injuring the stumps.

Costs

Investment cost	None no investment costs involved.
Average cost per year per hectare	Variable Derives solely from the cost of growing the associated crops and the greater difficulty in related agricultural practices. The cost is therefore highly variable in relation to the crops.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Higher Compared with conventional practice, costs tend to be higher, much depends on the type of intercropping. In particular, the costs are related to the greater difficulty in performing the cultivation operations and the cost of the crop chosen for intercropping.
Public support	None

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2- Sheet Cultivation technique: soil conditioners and fertilizers

Increasing the sustainability and efficiency of agricultural systems is also possible today through new cultivation techniques. For viticulture, there are innovative approaches for individual practices with the goal of achieving environmental, social and economic sustainability.

Inescapable goals for viticulture include increasing the quantity and quality of production while decreasing environmental impact, residue rates and operating costs to improve farm profitability.

To achieve these goals, there are various cultivation techniques that allow the carbon consumed during the humification process to be replenished in the soil, and that provide the essential nutrients for the growth and productivity of the crops grown.

Among the various strategies available are the use of different kinds of soil conditioners and fertilizers including:

- Organo-mineral fertilization
- Compost
- Woody residues
- Green residues
- Digestate
- Manure or organic soil conditioners
- Biochar
- Mycorrhizae

SHEET 2.1 – ORGANO-MINERAL FERTILIZER

Technical Description

The use of organo-mineral fertilizers is gaining considerable importance in the farm management field after years of exploitation of soils and excessive mineral fertilization. Indeed, organo-mineral fertilization can be viewed as a crucial technique for the vineyard as well.

Organo-mineral fertilizers are obtained by mixing and processing organic matrices and mineral fertilizers.

They can be obtained by reaction or by simple mixing of organic substances with mineral components. The choice of the best mineral components (soluble phosphorus, slow-release nitrogen, potassium from sulfate) and the use of highly humified organic matter play a key role on their activity in the field.

By virtue of their formulation, organo-mineral fertilizers contain nitrogen both in ready (mineral fraction) and slow (organic fraction) release form as a result of the mineralization processes that the organic matrix undergoes through the activity of the soil microorganisms. To guarantee the microorganism activity, the quality of the organic matter used in the formulation of the products, particularly its level of humification, is a fundamental factor. In fact, the presence of high amounts of humic substances is the basis of the cation exchange capacity of organo-mineral fertilizers and consequently of their protective effect towards nutrients, which are therefore released gradually and with a significant reduction in losses-as well as their buffering capacity.

The advantages of organo-mineral fertilization are: more efficient fertilization with complexed nutrients, lower environmental impact, compliance with production specifications, and higher crop profitability with lower inputs.

Costs

Average cost per year per hectare	Medium-high The costs per hectare for the work involved in this technique depend on the cost of fertilizers, which are normally more expensive than normal mineral fertilizers
Cost compared with conventional practice	Comparable
Public support	None

SHEET 2.2 – COMPOST

Technical Description

The low supply of organic matter is one of the major problems of Italian soils even more pronounced in those with a strong viticultural vocation, of which more than 50 percent is severely lacking.

Compost is the result of bio-oxidation and humification by macros and microorganisms of a mixture of organic matter (such as pruning residues, kitchen scraps,

manure, slurry) under special conditions: (i) presence of oxygen, and (ii) balance between the chemical elements of the matter involved in the transformation.

Applying compost to the vineyard, coupled with improved soil management (grass strips, minimum/no-tillage techniques, residue shredding) not only reduces the environmental impact of cultivation, but also provides a number of not insignificant pedo-agronomic benefits:

- Improved soil structure, porosity and water status: an additional 1% of carbon retained in the soil could increase the amount of water available to vines by 20%;
- Increased humic and fulvic acids contents, which, in addition to facilitating water infiltration into the soil after rainfall/irrigation, increase water storage capacity by providing better resilience to climate hazards;
- Improved soil microbial activity;
- Improved deepening and exploration capacity of the vine root system, which means providing better resilience to climatic hazards;
- Storage, both direct and indirect, of more carbon;
- Improved availability and improved soil mobility of plant-useful nutrients.

The use of compost has undoubtedly proven to be an agronomically effective source of organic matter. By improving soil fertility, compost can be used to supplement or replace to varying degrees chemical fertilization, the reduction of which can have important environmental repercussions: it increases biodiversity by promoting transformations, a phytosanitary effect that limits phytopathologies from soil-specific agents, and it promotes better workability of the soil by giving

it a more stable structure by reducing energy consumption. In addition, compost is characterized by a high content of stabilized organic matter, that has two important effects: the first is a general improvement in the chemical-physical characteristics of the soil, which is therefore safeguarded from erosion phenomena; the second is a progressive accumulation of carbon in the soil, with a carbon storage function (carbon sink) in the context of mitigate the greenhouse effect.

There is a wide choice of compost types, as well as different levels of application and burial strategies:

- Composted Green Manure (ACV), obtained exclusively from the selective collection of municipal and agricultural green waste mowing and pruning;
- Composted Mixed Amended (ACM), obtained from the matrices allowed for the production of ACV plus other matrices composed of: wet fraction of household waste (FORSU), plant residues, agro-food waste;
- Composted soil conditioner with sludge (ACF), obtained from the matrices allowed for the production of ACM plus sludge and wastewater of civil or agribusiness origin, in compliance with legal parameters.

Environmental benefits in addition to soil Carbon accumulation: **positive**

In the long run, it improves soil quality by increasing organic matter content and water retention capacity, with positive effects on quality and yield: compost input directly affects productivity, vegetative development, and grape quality. Its use improves both soil structure and the availability of nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen compounds). In addition, as a biological activator it increases microflora biodiversity and soil microbiological characteristics.

Biophysical and environmental limitations: **contamination risk**

Main limitation is the risk of physical and chemical contamination, related to the quality of the material that undergoes the composting process. Physical contaminations concern impurities that may be present. Chemical contaminations concern the excess of specific elements, e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus, or the presence of undesirable chemicals, both of which have the potential to cause harmful environmental effects. Among the risks of excessive compost use is nitrate leaching.

Technical limitations: **appropriate composting processes.**

To obtain compost of adequate quality, it is necessary to ensure an adequate composting process and associated maturation stage.

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Costs

Investment cost	Variable Costs vary according to the type of product: bulk - packaged - pelleted. Bulk product has an average cost that varies between 3 and 6 euros/ton. The quantity used varies depending on the crop, soil textural characteristics, and the percentage of background organic matter. The quantity used averages between 10-20 t/ha, which results in a total cost between 30 and 120 euros/ha. Compost input tends to decrease over the years, benefiting from the slow release of nutrients.
Average cost per year per hectare	Comparable Compost, depending on the crop and soil type, can replace all or part of non-organic fertilization.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Comparable
Public support	PSP – Rural Development Interventions. SRA04 – ACA4 – contribution of organic matter in soils.

SHEET 2.3- REUSE OF WOODY RESIDUES

Technical description

The ban on burning pruning residues in the field, in addition to those resulting from the removal of the vineyard, are strongly revolutionizing the technical-organizational choices of winegrowers and significantly weighing down production costs.

The use of wood residues has been extensively re-evaluated in recent years. They, in the form of pruning waste or as wood chips,

if buried significantly increase the content of stable carbon in the soil thanks to the high content of lignin. If used in massive quantities, without further action, they could cause a temporary loss of fertility due to the alteration of the carbon/nitrogen ratio in the soil. Over time, however, the soil gets numerous benefits both from a chemical and physical point of view. In particular, this practice improves soil water retention, creating excellent porosity. Providing structure to the soil helps combat erosion. In addition, in special cases, wood chips can be used as a natural mulching material, drastically reducing the evaporation of water from the ground.

The burial of the prunings in the vineyard can however constitute a source of inoculum of plant pathologies even important, so it could be more convenient to collect them in bales for the production of biochar, to be then applied again to the soil. The woody residues must be properly chopped, chopped and brittled through the use of mulches, and then buried in order to facilitate their rapid degradation by the soil microflora. To accelerate and improve the degradation of the shredded material, before the mechanical operation it is possible to distribute to the soil an appropriate quantity of manure or commercial products carrying useful microorganisms for the degradation of plant material. In the case of healthy plants, the practice has beneficial effects on soil. However, this practice should be avoided when pathogenic organisms are present in the wood of the plants (fungi, cancer agents, lead sickness, etc.) which, being able to live as saprophytes in the soil, take advantage of the woody residues considerably increasing the inoculum potential.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: **positive**

This method allows to preserve the soil structure, reduce the risk of erosion and runoff of the soil, improve the absorption and infiltration of water and increase the efficiency of irrigation. It also has a positive impact on biodiversity.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **Risk of plant pathologies spread**

This practice should be avoided when pathogenic organisms are present in the wood of plants (fungi, cancer agents, lead sickness, etc.) that, being able to live as saprophytes in the soil, take advantage of the woody residues greatly increasing the inoculum potential.

Technical limitations: **specific machining**

One of the limitations of technology is the cost and maintenance of mulching.

Costs

Investment cost	Medium-High The purchase of a mulcher can have a cost ranging from 4.000€ to 6.000€, its average life is about 12-15 years. Medium-sized farms of around 3-5 ha typically use only one mulcher, larger farms can use 2 or more. Small companies generally resort to subcontracting.
Average cost per year per hectare	Medium Considering an average depreciation of 800-1200€/ha, the cost per ha/year (including labour costs and energy) varies between 80 and 100€/ha/year. If you resort to the contractor the cost also varies from 100 € to 150 €/ha/year.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Unchanged The cost can be considered equal as it is now a matter of usual practice
Public support	PSP – Rural development interventions SRA21 - Action 2 Management of ground pruning residues SRD01 - agricultural production investments for the competitiveness of agricultural holdings (for the purchase of mulchers) SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare

SHEET 2.4 – REUSE OF GREEN WASTE

Technical Description

Green residues are a waste material resulting from twigs, pruning residues, foliage, hedge cuttings that take part in the composition of growing substrates. Shredded and placed in compost heaps are intended for re-use as compost. However, organic residues generated by routine maintenance of green areas such as cuttings and pruning should preferably be composted on site or «in situ» chips and, where technically possible, used as mulch in suitable areas to reduce the phenomenon of evaporation from the ground.

In the case of large waste, it is possible to reduce them to smaller sizes by turning them into wood chips by means of bio-shredders (biochippators or wood chippers) and then to be accumulated in the compost bin to produce soil. Green residues bring carbon and nutrients in a balanced way back to the soil in a carbon sink perspective, in order to support less impactful company guidelines in terms of the use of productive inputs, and contributing to the growth of organic matter positively affect fertility and available water. In addition, straw, clippings and leaves can be used as mulching material to drastically reduce evaporation.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: positive

This method allows to preserve the soil structure, reduce the risk of erosion and runoff of the soil, improve the absorption and infiltration of water and increase the efficiency of irrigation. It also has a positive impact on biodiversity.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: logistic difficulties

A potential obstacle to the exploitation of by-products is represented by the logistical factor, since residues and waste are often produced in many small-medium production companies and in different periods of the crop cycle. This makes their collection, concentration and management expensive, especially if they are by-products with high perishability that need to be quickly subjected to the composting processes.

Technical limitations:

As for compost, it is necessary to ensure an adequate composting process and its maturation phase.

Costs

Investment cost	High The purchase of a mulcher can have a cost ranging from 4.000 € to 6.000 € and its average life is about 12-15 years. Companies of medium size, 3-5 ha, usually use only one shredder, the largest can use 2 or more, while small companies generally resort to subcontracting.
Average cost per year per hectare	Not excessive Considering an average depreciation of 50-80€/ha the cost per ha/year (including labour costs and energy) varies between 120 and 150€/ha/year. If you have recourse to the contractor the cost also varies from 120 € to 150 €/ha/year
Cost compared with conventional practice	Higher
Public support	PSP - Rural development interventions SRA21 – Action 2 Management of ground pruning residues SRD01 - agricultural production investments for the competitiveness of agricultural holdings (for the purchase of mulchers) SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare

SHEET 2.5 – DIGESTATE

Technical Description

Digestate is the result of the anaerobic digestion process of various materials, mainly livestock effluents, vegetable biomass and animal and/or agro-industrial by-products. Digestate improves the physical and chemical properties of the soil and can act as a substitute for some fertilizers, increasing yields with the same amount of other resources used.

The agronomic use of digestate as a fertilizer

allows both the contribution of nutritional elements to replace synthetic and organic fertilizers, and the possibility of closing the biogeochemical cycle of carbon and nutrients. Used after solid-liquid separation, it allows to make the most of the characteristics of fertilizer: the solid fraction, with its soil-conditioning properties, is used as an alternative to organic fertilization (compost), while the liquid fraction, rich in readily assimilable nitrogen (68.9% N-NH₄/N tot) can be used as a replacement for mineral fertilisers (urea).

Solid digestate contributes to the enrichment of carbon in soil (more stable than that of sewage), while liquid digestate returns moisture due to the high water content. It is advisable to inject digestate below the surface to avoid the loss of nitrogen by volatilisation, which is mainly found in ammoniacal form.

It is important to adequately dose the amount of the digestate in order to avoid adverse effects. The optimal management of digestate (dosing and periods of use) in fact allows to minimize emissions of ammonia and greenhouse gases both during storage and distribution. The fertigation distribution of digestate does not cause any form of leaching or percolation of nitrogen compounds in the deep layers of soil, keeping nutrients in the first 50 cm without polluting groundwater.

In relation to the organic nature of the digestate itself, the quantification of spreading volumes must be supported by constant monitoring of soil fertility and adaptation of the company's fertilisation plan, so that it can be assessed the overall effect produced by digestate.

The use of digestate, when fully exploited from the agronomic point of view, allows to achieve a complete substitution of the mineral fertilizations, avoid the risk of soil salinisation due to the accumulation of micro-elements and preserve the chemical and microbiological balance of the soil

with significant environmental and economic benefits, without altering the production yield of the crops.

Digestate must therefore be considered as a "renewable organic fertilizer" with high environmental value, immediate effect, complete, and balanced. As well as for the spreading of manure, also for digestate a greater fertilizer efficiency is obtained by using adequate mechanization and efficient spreading techniques. It is obviously fundamental the analytical knowledge of the fertilizer content (NPK) for the application of volumes that meet the nutritional needs of the crop, in compliance with the constraints of the nitrate legislation.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: positive

It allows an intake of organic substance and NPK elements, such as to represent a valid alternative to synthetic fertilizers, minimizing ammonia emissions.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: limitations of use

The Nitrates Directive limits the quantities of digestate derived from manure in the field (170 kg/ha/year for vulnerable zones). Obstacles are also present for the construction and operation of the plants, for which the authorization process is very complex.

Technical limitations: emissions, leaching or percolation of nitrogen compound

Possible problems related to the agronomic use of digestate:

- nitrate losses in water, if applied during inappropriate periods in excessive doses,
- ammonia emissions into the atmosphere, when not adequately distributed.

Costs

Investment cost	<p>Very High</p> <p>The purchase of distribution machinery has a variable cost depending on the different models: self-propelled vehicles with high working capacity, tank capacity, equipped with volumetric pumps and precision dosers, tested discs or with drip wings or with bar with drops. The cost for a self-propelled vehicle varies on average from 500.000€ to 700.000€ and it is generally purchased by contractors. The purchase of barrel with underground (mainly company equipment, lasting about 12 years) the cost varies on average between 120.000 € and 180.000€. This equipment is generally aimed at farms with livestock.</p>
Average cost per year per hectare	<p>Medium</p> <p>Normally, due to high cost for the equipment, the application is made by use of external contractors. The average annual cost per hectare varies between 240 € and 300 € whereas the cost of the contractor is about 4 € per cubic meter and in one hectare are distributed about 60 cubic meters. In the case of own production of digestate and possession of equipment, an estimated depreciation, maintenance, diesel fuel and labour cost of about 150-180 €/ha is estimated.</p>
Cost compared with conventional practice	<p>Higher</p> <p>The cost of the practice is higher, but would be in partial replacement of synthetic fertilizers, with economic savings and an environmental advantage.</p>
Public support	<p>PSP – Rural Development Interventions</p> <p>SRA04 - ACA4 - contribution of organic substance in soils; SRD01 - agricultural productive investments for the competitiveness of agricultural holdings (purchase of machinery); SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare.</p>

SHEET 2.6 – MANURE OR ORGANIC SOIL IMPROVERS

Technical Description

The distribution of organic products has always been important from the agronomic point of view and today, after years of exploitation of soils and mineral fertilizations not very rational, has become a necessity.

Certainly organic fertilizations represent a rather high cost and do not give an immediate productive and

therefore economic return, but to reverse or at least slow down the current trend of organic matter loss of land it can be viewed as a medium-long-term investment, time-span where it positively affect soil physical chemical and biological characteristics.

Stable manure, or manure, which is obtained from the solid and liquid excreta of the animals in housing, mixed with materials of various origins constituting the litter, following more or less intense fermentation is one of the most ancient and well none manure. It is a material of more or less heterogeneous consistency, of variable composition, with variable characteristics depending on the type and quantity of litter, the type of animal that produced it, the production technique, of conservation and fermentation.

Autumn is the most suitable period for organic fertilization in the vineyards in production: low temperatures and soil humidity allow the good humification of the distributed substance. The contribution of manure for the fertilization of vineyard production can be expected in about 10 tons per hectare, but this dose can be increased by 30-40% in sandy soils or rich in skeleton, tendentially warm and arid, since in these situations the mineralization of organic matter is very accelerated. Manure can be distributed manually or using special spreader wagons equipped with horizontal spreading rollers, able to orient the product along the row. The manure distributed on the ground must then be partially buried with a slight mechanical operation.

The use of manure can be replaced using dried and pelletized products, which can be distributed with normal fertilizer spreaders. In this case the dose must be appropriately reduced according to the content of fertilizer elements declared on the package (indicative doses per hectare are reduced to about 1-1.5 tons per hectare).

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: **positive**

Among the benefits that this material brings to the field, we remember the increase of organic substance and the improvement of soil structure, with a better ability to retain water. It is advisable to bury the manure in order not to frustrate most of its advantages.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **limitations of use**

A good manure must be left to mature for at least three months, with a good composition (with a good supply of straw and other litters) and at an affordable price. For all these reasons, as well as for the decrease of animal breeding using this type of excreta management, nowadays the manure is difficult to find and is rather expensive. It is recommended to give priority to composted manure as it is stabilized, cleaned of possible fungi, bacteria, viruses, etc. as well as weed seeds due to the temperatures reached during composting. In fact, in it the nutrients are in the most available form and cannot damage the plants since it does not «heat» more and has lost the most aggressive nitrogen forms (ammonia).

Technical limitations: **variable composition, difficult distribution**

Manure is always useful, but the animal species from which it derives (cattle, horses, sheep, etc.) and the origin of the litter (cereal straw, corn stalks, shavings, hay, etc.) diversify its composition and characteristics and, as a result, optimal conditions of use.

Transport and distribution are very expensive, it is necessary to distribute it in a uniform way, so that all the mass of the soil can benefit and do not form «lumps» that make problematic the sowing and the development of plants.

Costs

Investment cost	<p>High</p> <p>The purchase of spreader machines varies depending on the spreading system, on the back or on the side of the wagon. Costs are reduced if a contractor is employed. The cost of spreader cart can vary on average between 30.000 € and 50.000 € and the duration is about 10/12 years.</p>
Average cost per year per hectare	<p>Medium-High</p> <p>In case the manure is farm and is managed with farm equipment the annual cost per hectare varies on average between 150€ and 200€ (depreciation, diesel, equipment maintenance, work). In case of contractors the cost varies on average between 250 € to 300 € /ha. The cost is related to the purchase of manure, loading, transport and spreading. The cost/ha can vary considerably according to the needs of the soil and the crops, the manure intake is calibrated according to the needs of soil conditioning power.</p> <p>The practice has economic advantages linked to the improvement of yields and the saving of fertilizers. The farms that have the greatest advantages in using manure are those that produce manure directly and those located close to livestock farms, which have a lower incidence of transport costs.</p>
Cost compared with conventional practice	<p>Variable</p> <p>It depends on the type and cost of synthetic fertilizers that are replaced by manure. The practice has economic advantages linked to the improvement of yields and the saving of fertilizers.</p>
Public support	<p>PSP – Rural development interventions</p> <p>SRA04 - ACA4 - contribution of organic substance in soils; SRD01 - agricultural productive investments for the competitiveness of agricultural holdings (purchase of machinery); SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare.</p>

SHEET 2.7 – BIOCHAR

Technical Description

The decrease in the number of rainy days, the increase in the intensity of individual climatic events and the rise in temperature have negative effects on the whole agricultural sector, including viticulture, where water stress affects grape production and wine quality. To mitigate the effects of climate change, therefore, sustainable agronomic strategies must be adopted that improve the adaptability

of the vine, including the use of biochar, a soil improver obtained from the pyrolysis/gasification of plant biomass, Carbon rich and can improve soil structure. The use of biochar is listed among the techniques of "Carbon Removal".

Biochar is the charcoal obtained from the pyrolysis of different types of plant biomass. Of particular interest is its production from residues/ agricultural by-products: pruning, stubble of corn or wheat, rice husk, almond husk, dry foliage, etc. Pyrolysis allows to obtain: a gas (syngas) with a calorific value equal to LPG that can be used in production processes that require heat (eg: drying for farms processes or for the production of electricity), and biochar or charcoal. Biochar is therefore the by-product of pyrolysis which, when applied to soils, is a powerful soil improver (90% carbon content). Its high porosity increases water and nutrients retention that remain longer available for plants; it also improves soil structure and mechanical properties. Many studies have already shown the positive impact of the application of biochar on agricultural yields by reducing the need for water and fertilizers. The compact structure of the biochar allows this product a low degradability by soil microorganisms and therefore to store carbon instead of returning it to the atmosphere in the form of CO₂ as in the case of compost or the shortening of pruning residues. The use of biochar on agricultural land reduces N₂O emissions from soil, a greenhouse gas with a global warming potential 296 times greater than CO₂. Its use in alkaline soils should be carefully evaluated, as it could increase salinity and, in specific cases, deactivate the active ingredients of herbicides. At present in Italy, there is still no real market for biochar.

In viticulture biochar is used in order to improve the chemical, physical and biological fertility of soils, the ability to retain nutrients and increase water infiltration and as a long-term storage mechanism for carbon. Moreover, it remains stable in the soil for very long periods bringing continuous benefits to the soil-plant system.

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In viticulture, the combination of biochar with organic soil improvers such as manure and digestate seems to be very promising. Some experiments have been carried out in France to produce biochar from grape marc, but the results are still being updated.

Other experiments previously conducted in Italy have clearly shown an increase in yield under water stress conditions, without alteration of grape quality, applying a high amount of biochar (i.e 22 tons per hectare) on sandy soils. However, this is a very large amount. An Italian research estimated that to produce 0.5 tons of biochar 1 hectare of vineyard is needed. This means that to produce the biochar necessary for the enrichment of a single hectare, using only the biomass resources of the vineyard, 44 hectares of vineyards would be needed. Consequently, the use of biochar in vineyards cannot be separated from the intervention of external suppliers, with important logistical challenges to be solved.

Another Italian study in 2017 showed a significant increase in soil carbon sequestration, as well as in the water and ammonium available for the vine, by applying 10 tons of biochar per hectare. More importantly, researchers have observed a direct effect of biochar in stimulating plant growth and increasing the life expectancy of thinner roots.

At present, the cost of applying biochar depends on many variables in the supply chain, e.g. production process, distance between production and distribution location, distributed quantities and distribution modes. Currently there is still a reference price in the Italian market, but a study by the Italian Biochar Association (ICHAR) has estimated the variability of costs on the international market, in a range from 40 to 4500 €/ton (production, transport and distribution in the field). The distribution can take place in a single solution or be divided into several applications, it is usually distributed with several interventions, or with a single passage on small plots. The recommended dose is between 10/20 and 60 tons per hectare, depending on the nature of the soil.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: **positive**

Biochar has many qualities: high and very stable carbon content, high pH, high porosity leading to a large contact surface. This potentially makes it a valuable soil enrichment. The key role remains in the mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions (carbon sequestration) and adaptation to climate change (improved water retention).

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **contamination risk**

The biochar may contain contaminants that, above certain levels, compromise its quality and use, causing adverse effects on the environment and health. The contaminants present in the biochar can be more or less mobile, that is migrate in the area (volatilization) or in the water (solubilization). Contaminants may include: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), Dioxins, Furans, Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) and heavy metals.

Technical limitations: **variability in composition and origin, stringent regulation**

It is not a product with constant characteristics: its properties and composition depend very much on the type of biomass used and the conditions for pyrolysis.

There are many types of biochar with different characteristics in relation to the type of vegetable biomass used, the type and temperature of pyrolysis, the use of which must be weighted on the type of soil, climate and agronomic technique.

The lack of a specific European directive on biochar has led many European nations to recognise it under their own legislation. The Italian legislation allows biochar in agriculture to 100%, but sets limits to any pollutants present within the biochar and requires those who sell or produce in their own biochar to produce a special certification of analysis.

Costs

Investment cost	<p>None</p> <p>It is assumed that the production is not made by the farm but by specialised plants</p>
Average cost per year per hectare	<p>Very high</p> <p>If the biochar production process is exclusively aimed at the production of biochar, without recovery of the energy produced during the process, the production costs are very high. In Italy, according to some research studies, in the case of lignocellulosic residual biomass (zero value, except transport), the cost of biochar is about 500-1000 €/t, but may have much higher quotations concerning the commercially available formulation.</p>
Cost compared with conventional practice	<p>Much higher</p> <p>The cost depends on the difficult availability of the material, its low specific weight and the difficult ways of distribution in the field.</p>
Public support	<p>PSP – Rural development interventions</p> <p>SRA04 - ACA4 - contribution of organic substance in soils; SRD01 - agricultural productive investments for the competitiveness of agricultural holdings (purchase of machinery); SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare.</p>

SHEET 2.8 – MYCORRHIZAE

Technical Description

The importance of fertility and microbiological vitality of the soil in viticulture is an evidence that puts in agreement all the productive orientations, from integrated to organic, from biodynamic to natural. The symbiosis between plant roots and mycorrhizas helps create the conditions for greater efficiency in mineral and water nutrition, as well as

to increase the plant's resistance to stress, through the hyphal network that determines the transfer of resistance signals to fungal pathogens.

Mycorrhiza is a symbiotic association between a fungus commonly present in soils and a plant defined as superior and represents the classic case of mutual symbiosis, or interaction of different organisms aimed at mutual benefit: the endophyte (fungus) receives trophic support (feeding) from the plant, which in turn benefits from improved absorption of mineral elements and water, ensuring vegetative vigor and resistance to pests and environmental stresses.

Mycorrhizas represent the most common form of symbiosis between microorganisms (fungi, in this case) and higher plants, since the roots of most plants are mycotic. About 83% of dicotyledons and 79% of monocotyledons and all gymnosperms can be considered mycotic (Marschner, 1995). The association between the fungus and the upper plant is usually a mutual symbiosis, although not always so. As a function of how the fungal mycelium relates to the root, also based on structural, functional and taxonomic criteria the mycorrhizas are classified in: ectomycorrhizas and endomycorrhizas.

Ectomycorrhizas are a class of mycorrhizae belonging to the species Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes and characterized by the lack of penetration inside the host cells. The ectomycorrhizal fungus forms, in the apical portion of the root, a mycelial sheath called micoclen or mantle. From micoclena develop the hyphae that creep between the cells of the cortical parenchyma of the root going to form the Hartig lattice through which exchanges of sugars produced by the plant and water and mineral salts absorbed by the fungus. Under appropriate conditions, the hyphae of the lattice extend in the soil leading to the production of reproductive structures called carpophores (e.g. truffles and edible mushrooms). This class of mycorrhizas is prevalent mainly in woody plants of temperate forests while they are scarcely present in herbaceous species.

Endomycorrhizas differ from ectomycorrhizas in their ability to interact with the host plant's root cells while not producing the external fungal mantle. Their interest from the agricultural point of view is given by the ability to colonize up to 95% of plant species. Endomycorrhiza have been found in extensive species (maize and soya) with the exception of beet, fruit species, vegetable species with the exception of cruciferous (e.g. cabbage) and chenopodiacee (e.g. spinach) but also broad-leaved and coniferous. These fungi can also be found in pioneering environments such as sand dunes (Rea et al. 2013)

The mycorrhizas of the genus *Glomus* spp, a type of endophytic fungi, colonizing the root system of the host plants, create a network of fungal structures called hyphae capable of exploring a greater volume of soil than the root system alone, improving the passage of nutrients to the plant. Hyphae also contribute to the improvement of the soil structure, optimizing the formation of aggregates. Mycorrhizal fungus supplies the root with nutrients, especially phosphates, thanks to an extensive extra-radical mycelial network, and increases resistance to abiotic stress (drought, salinity and heavy metals) and biotics (soil pathogens); in exchange, the host plant yields part of the photosynthetes. Mycorrhizas are able to assimilate very complex organic phosphorus forms that cannot be assimilated by plants such as phytin; moreover, they possess much stronger phosphatases, which are able to release insoluble inorganic phosphorus.

Plants are activated to absorb phosphorus by emitting substances attractive to mycorrhizal fungi in order to establish with them a mutual symbiosis that guarantees the fungus a balanced nutrition and, to plants, a sufficient availability of phosphorus.

Mycorrhizal fungi live in all soils, but are particularly common in sub-acidic natural environments. In agricultural cultivated land, their spread is much reduced due to the processing and massive use of synthetic antifungal products and/or the presence of heavy metals present as contaminated. Also the reduction of the content in organic matter due to the continuous processing and the alkalization of agricultural soils due to urea fertilizations leads to a decrease in the development of these fungi.

The use of mycorrhizas has therefore the purpose of accelerating the vegetative development of the income crop in the very first phases of growth, to increase its productive efficiency.

In viticulture is a technique generally limited to nursery to accelerate the development of the root system. However, mycorrhizas can be applied also to the soil through mycorrhizal inoculums present in different formulations such as granules and microgranules, concentrated liquids and powders. Usually, the inoculant in the form of granules and microgranules are distributed before the transplant of the culture that is to be mycorrhized. However, it can be applied also in the field. At vineyard planting, the inoculant can be placed in the transplant hole and covered with a slight layer of soil, and then the plant is planted. During the growing season, liquid formulations and soluble powders can be applied immediately after transplantation or later through the irrigation system. This method is beneficial for a second application using the localized irrigation system.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: **positive**

Mycorrhized plants tolerate more climatic changes by enhancing the yield and quality of production, and reduce water requirements, in fact, mycorrhization increases the water supply capacity. In addition, they improve the soil structure making it more oxygenated and less susceptible to erosion.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **strong influence of soil condition**

The mycorrhization is absent in very dry, brackish, asphyxiated pedoclimatic environments or where the soil is very fertile or very poor.

Technical limitations:

No technical limitations

Costs

Average cost per year per hectare Investment cost	Low Costs per hectare depend on the type of plant and the type of crop. The average cost generally varies from 70 to 200 euro/ha per year.
Cost compared with conventional practice	Slightly higher
Public support	None

3- Crop data sheets: Irrigation

The vine is a plant with limited water needs, but to obtain a good product it is essential to meet its irrigation needs. In some wine-growing areas, where rainfall and soil characteristics do not guarantee adequate water availability, irrigation is necessary to avoid water stress. The effects of water stress on the vine can vary in severity depending on the period and phenological phase in which it occurs: for example, a water stress in flowering can cause falling and leaking and impairs the development of new hibernating buds; a stress when the colours begin to turn (during veraison in summer) leads to a deterioration of the organoleptic characteristics of the product and an interruption of the ripening processes of the berries; finally, a water stress at the final stage of maturation can improve the quality of the wine, for a reduction in water concentration and an increase in sugar concentration.

It is possible to recognize two main types of irrigation systems used in farms: ordinary or emergency irrigation systems.

Ordinary irrigation is defined as that covering the annual cycle of the vine (April-September) in areas with very low rainfall (<100 mm), characterized by regular irrigation interventions during the season (Marenghi, 2007). *Emergency irrigation* is that used in areas where the quantity of rain in the growing season is theoretically sufficient (150-400 mm) for plants' needs, but due to the high variability of rainfall frequency is difficult to predict the time, duration and extent of water stress and the irrigation is made "on demand" (Marenghi, 2007).

Generally, except for wine-growing areas where irrigation is essential for the plant to complete its life cycle and improve the quality of the grapes, irrigation tends to increase vegetative activity, at the expense of the ripening of the berries. Excessive use can cause a delay in ripening, leading to a lower quality product.

The irrigation methods used for the vine are mainly micro-irrigation (see the dedicated section) and sprinkler irrigation.

Sprinkler irrigation, which mimics the rainfall, does not require high installation costs but is considered less efficient than drip irrigation due to higher water loss due to evaporation and runoff. Therefore, it is to be used only as the last tool available to the winegrower to save production and it cannot be considered as the business as usual practice.

SHEET 3.1 – MICRO-IRRIGATION - DRIP IRRIGATION

Technical Description

Micro-irrigation, in particular drip irrigation is widespread in the cultivation of vines, especially in temperate areas with scarce water resources. This type of irrigation is suitable for soils with irregular shape or where the topography or consistency of the soil is not uniform. This system supplies water in a slow and uniform way at low pressure, by means of plastic pipes installed close to the area of the roots of the plants in which the drippers are inserted. A well-designed system optimizes the use of water as it reduces runoff, evaporation or deep percolation in the silty soil. To ensure efficient operation of the drippers along each irrigation line, it is crucial to design the system for uniform water

distribution to each dripper. Self-compensating drippers, which regulate the water flow at each point, and anti-drainage drippers, which prevent air from entering the pipes, are available on the market. The installation of devices for automatic systems and precise programming of irrigation increases performance and quality, saves work load time and adapts dynamically to climatological or production conditions. The prerogative of these tool is to allow to set "tailor-made" irrigation cycles. Equally easy is the reading of the stored parameters and their modification in response to climatic changes or new operational needs.

The management of irrigation must always be dynamically articulated according to the physical characteristics of the soil, the seasonal trend, the age and the vigour of the plants.

Environmental benefits in addition to the accumulation of carbon in the soil: **positive**

The drip irrigation system protects all production (100%) from drought events and also allows the area between rows to be kept dry, reducing the proliferation of weeds and the risk of combustion. The product is healthier and more uniform, even the yields are higher. The plants are put in the best conditions to express maximum productivity. Water contact with foliage, stems and fruits is reduced, creating conditions less favourable to the development of diseases in plants or crops. This system reduces the use of pesticides and the loss of nitrates, since the application of water, and therefore fertigation, is limited to the area of the roots of the plant. There is also greater energy savings linked to lower water consumption.

Bio-physical and environmental limitations: **Water salinity**

The even moderate salinity of irrigated water is a serious problem for all crops and in particular for those very sensitive, where the accumulation of salts in the soil would cause serious repercussions on the growth and productivity of crops.

Technical limitations:

The technique is easily implemented, but requires information, preparation and attention by the technician and the farmer to irrigation practice.

The presence of elements in suspension or in solution in the water, leads to the risk of clogging the drippers, with a drastic worsening of the uniformity and efficiency of the system. The removal of suspended elements by filtration, and that of the elements in solution (acidification and other techniques) it is difficult and very expensive.

Costs

Investment cost	<p>High</p> <p>In viticulture the cost of the plant (including design) varies from 1.500€/ha to 4.000€/ha depending on the type of soil and slope, the latter can affect with a cost increase of between 5 and 10%. The cost for the installation of the system varies from 600€/ha to 1.000€/ha. The total investment cost therefore varies on average from 2.100€/ha to 5.000€/ha. The estimated plant life is 10-15 years and over.</p>
Average cost per year per hectare	<p>High</p> <p>The annual maintenance cost of a drip irrigation system varies from 200 to 300 €/ha. Considering a linear depreciation of 10 years, the annual cost/ha and maintenance, it is estimated an annual cost/ha variable on average from 400€/ha to 800€/ha.</p>
Cost compared with conventional practice	<p>Low</p> <p>This system allows a great saving of water and energy of about 30-40% compared to traditional irrigation.</p>
Public support	<p>PSP – Rural Development Interventions</p> <p>SRD01 - agricultural productive investments for the competitiveness of farms;</p> <p>SRD02 - agricultural productive investments for environment, climate and animal welfare;</p> <p>SRA24 - ACA24 - precision agriculture practices (intervention that finances the precision agriculture technique and not the necessary investment, financed by SRD01);</p>

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